

METHODS OF USING MUSICAL MEANS IN TEACHING THE HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN IN A SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: In this article, the methodology of teaching music is a field of pedagogy that studies the process of teaching history and music in order to use its laws to further increase the effectiveness of teaching, education and personal development. Music is an emotional stimulus that helps you translate inner experiences into words. The educational process consists of the following interrelated and interconnected components: educational goals, content, teacher's activities, student activities and results.

Keywords: teacher activity, student activity, learning process, teaching methods, branch of music, teaching history.

The methodology of teaching history is a branch of pedagogical science that studies the process of teaching history in order to use its patterns to further improve the effectiveness of training, education and development of the individual. The subject of the methodology of teaching history is the process of teaching history. The learning process can be defined as a change in learning acts occurring according to objective laws, during which the activities of the teacher and students change, as well as the properties of students as a result of their activities. The learning process consists of the following interrelated and interdependent components: learning objectives, content, teacher activities, student activities and results. The methodology of teaching history explores how, with the help of what methods, means and techniques to ensure the most accessible, visual, concrete and convincing perception, understanding and assimilation of historical facts; what methods and means to ensure the memorization of these facts, how to reveal the studied phenomena in the most accessible way, how to organize the active mental work of students so that the revealed phenomena are assimilated and help further knowledge. The task of methodology as a science is to explore the natural connections between the various aspects of education and, on the basis of the learned patterns, develop requirements for the subject, teaching and learning, ensure that students deeply assimilate the basics of historical science and educate them in a humanistic worldview.

Any activity, in particular, intellectual, is provided by the functional work of the brain associated with the perception and processing of information. The functional capabilities of the human body have remained unchanged since ancient times, and in our time, you need to know and be able to do much more.

Due to the increase in training loads, problems arise in children: stress, increased anxiety, fatigue, deterioration of children's health in general.

Teaching methods in the school system are mainly focused on the left hemisphere of the brain. The left hemisphere is responsible for speech and language abilities, reading and writing abilities. It also remembers facts, names, dates, numbers, and math symbols. Helps to process information logically and consistently.

The right hemisphere, specializes in processing information, which is expressed not in words, but in images, gives us the opportunity to dream and fantasize, compose various stories, and is also responsible for the ability to music, dance and fine arts. But in the learning process, it is practically not involved.

The task of the teacher in the lesson is to use both hemispheres of the student's brain. Modern life requires such pedagogical technologies, which should, on the one hand, provide children with high-quality deep knowledge, creating an intellectual base for subsequent learning, and on the other hand, focus on the physical, mental, spiritual health of the child and take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of each age.

The human brain perceives music simultaneously in both hemispheres. The body of a person listening to music, as it were, adapts to it. As a result, the mood and working capacity rise, pain sensitivity decreases, sleep normalizes, a stable heart rate and breathing are restored.

The history of music, sometimes referred to as historical musicology, is a highly diverse area of the broader discipline of musicology that studies music from a historical perspective. In theory, "history of music" could refer to the study of the history of any type or genre of music.

Music is an art form in which musical sounds are organized in a certain way as a means of embodying artistic images. The main elements and expressive means of music are mode, rhythm, meter, tempo, loud dynamics, timbre, melody, harmony, polyphony, instrumentation.

The history of music in Iran (Persia) dates back to the prehistoric era. The legendary great king, Jamshid, is credited with inventing music. Music in Iran can be traced back to the days of the Elamite Empire (2500-644 BC). Some historians suggest that music originated from natural sounds. Thunder, the

rustle of leaves, the sound of rain, were the prototype of the first musical series. Others are sure that music originated from human speech: a sing-song drawl of words. 530 BC e. The philosopher and mystic Pythagoras is credited with the first attempts to explain music, in particular the intervals between sounds, using mathematics, as well as establishing a connection between these intervals and the movement of the planets. It makes us better, inspires and inspires, gives unforgettable feelings. It is thanks to music that a person is able to relax, rest, get certain food for the mind. This type of art is able to radically change the mood of a person - to cheer him up, sadden him, feel longing. Darwin considered music a sexual lure. Others believe that it was created to strengthen social ties, with its help, primitive people united in permanent groups. The study quite convincingly confirms the theory that "music appeared and developed in the process of life in a team".

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